

PRACTICAL FORMS AND METHODS OF COOPERATION BETWEEN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES AND CITIZENS' SELF-GOVERNMENT BODIES

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Abstract. This article provides a scientific and legal analysis of the practical forms and methods of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies. Specifically, it highlights the mechanisms for planning, implementation, summarization of results, and mutual assistance. The importance of integration between digital technologies and the mahalla institution in ensuring public safety is also substantiated.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, mahalla, cooperation, public safety, crime prevention, digital transformation, information exchange.

Cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies plays a crucial role in ensuring public safety, preventing offenses, and improving the system of working with the population. This cooperation is manifested not only through information exchange but also through the joint planning, implementation, and evaluation of practical activities.

Today, there is a growing need for rapid decision-making and the establishment of effective management in the field of public safety. From this perspective, the scientific analysis and improvement of the forms and methods of practical cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the "mahalla seven" is a pressing issue. Digital transformation processes, in turn, serve to further enhance the effectiveness of this cooperation.

In addition to information exchange, the forms of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies include a number of practical forms of collaboration. These forms encompass: a) planning of cooperation; b) joint implementation of measures; c) joint summarization of activity results; d) mutual assistance and support in the joint performance of tasks.

Planning of Cooperation. Planning refers to the process by which internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies define goals and objectives for the upcoming period to ensure public safety, protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, prevent and combat crime and offenses, identify the methods and means to achieve them, and also schedule the sequence and deadlines for their implementation.

Analysis shows that cooperation plans are classified based on the following criteria:

1) By form of expression: strategy, concept, joint resolution, program, roadmap, memorandum, and work plan.

These strategic documents were developed primarily at the national level and are aimed at implementing the "Safe Mahalla" principle, maintaining public order, strengthening public safety, and improving the crime prevention system. They include long-term comprehensive goals and serve to organize work in the regions based on the "mahallabay," "oilabay," and "fuqarobay" approaches.

These include, for example, the "Concept of Targeted Measures for Crime Prevention in Mahallas with a Complex Crime Situation"[1], the "Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of

Uzbekistan"[2], the "Strategy for the Development of the Public Safety System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2025,"[3] and the "Roadmap" for the effective implementation of the system based on the "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla" principle in the country[4]. This strategy, concept, and roadmaps allow for the organization of work based on "mahallabay," "oilabay," and "fuqarobay" models of mutual targeted cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies in ensuring public safety based on the "safe mahalla" principle.

2) According to the scope of implementation: a) republican; b) Republic of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent city and regions; c) district, city; d) planning at the level of mahallas.

a) cooperation plans at the national level - Cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies at the national level consists of defining comprehensive measures aimed at ensuring a "safe environment" in mahallas, maintaining public order, strengthening public safety, and organizing crime prevention. At the same time, the content of the programs to be implemented, their implementation mechanisms, specific deadlines, and responsible executors will be determined. Thus, cooperation activities at the national level will be coordinated based on a unified systematic approach, ensuring executive discipline and effectiveness.

b) Cooperation plans at the level of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the city of Tashkent, and the regions - These plans serve to organize cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies at the level of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the city of Tashkent, and the regions. They aim to curb crime at the mahalla level, prevent crimes and offenses at an early stage, and establish work based on the "mahallabay" and "fuqarobay" systems. Based on this, relevant "Roadmaps" will be developed, and specific measures for the implementation of the assigned tasks will be jointly implemented.

c) cooperation plans at the district and city levels - These plans organize cooperation activities at the district (city) level between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies aimed at curbing crime, early prevention of crimes and offenses, and the practical implementation of the "safe mahalla" principle in the context of mahallas. To this end, a "Roadmap" will be developed, which will clearly define the names of all measures, their implementation mechanisms, deadlines, necessary financial resources and sources of financing, as well as the entities responsible for their implementation.

d) cooperation plans at the mahalla level - At the mahalla level, a targeted work plan will be developed to be implemented throughout the year with the participation of the mahalla "seven" - the mahalla chairperson, hokim's assistant, women's activist, youth leader, social worker, tax inspector, and prevention inspector. This plan is aimed at resolving pressing socio-legal issues in the mahalla, strengthening public order, and effectively organizing preventive measures, and is approved by the relevant responsible leaders.

An important stage in cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies is the organization of early crime prevention in mahallas, the creation of a "safe environment," and planning aimed at maintaining public order and ensuring public safety. At the same time, the implementation of the planned activities will serve as the main practical stage of cooperation.

However, an analysis of practice shows that although many measures are planned within the framework of cooperation, not all of them are fully and effectively implemented. This creates a need to strengthen the continuity between planning and practical implementation, strengthen executive discipline, and improve the monitoring system.

Implementation of joint measures. Etymologically, the term "realization" comes from the Latin word "realis," which means "real," "material," or "materialized." In modern scientific and practical literature, this term is primarily used in the sense of implementing plans, programs, projects, and set goals into practice, i.e., fulfilling them in real life[5].

The form of interaction between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies, as well as planning, is carried out at the republican, regional (city), district (city), and mahalla levels. In this process, the joint execution of tasks defined between state bodies and mahalla institutions is of great importance.

Specifically, within the framework of ensuring the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-113 dated March 4, 2024, "On the preparation and holding of the national holiday of Navruz in 2024," the Association of Mahallas of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with the Ministry of Internal Affairs and its territorial divisions, will implement the tasks set for organizing the "Navruz" holiday in mahallas at the national level and conducting the "Hashar" nationwide movement, which is one of the national values.

Furthermore, in cooperation with internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies, it is planned to implement the "Attendance" event aimed at improving student attendance in secondary schools within the mahalla, the "Tiğ" event aimed at preventing delinquency among minors and youth, as well as the "Tun" preventive event aimed at strengthening control in nightclubs, bars, and internet cafes within the mahalla.

However, an analysis of practice shows that in some mahallas, these activities are not carried out in a targeted, systematic, and carefully planned manner. This reduces the effectiveness of preventive work and creates the need for further improvement of cooperation mechanisms.

Summarizing the results of the joint event. It is important to summarize the results of the joint work carried out by the subjects of cooperation, to identify the achievements and existing shortcomings, to achieve higher efficiency in the future, and to summarize the results of activities in order to improve the cooperation system. This process allows for an objective assessment of the activities carried out and the formulation of scientific and practical conclusions for subsequent stages.

Within the framework of the "Safe Mahalla" concept of internal affairs bodies, it is important to determine the results of the work carried out in cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, maintain public order, ensure public safety, prevent crime, transform the mahalla into a crime-free zone, and stabilize the criminogenic situation.

It is also necessary to objectively assess the effectiveness of cooperation activities, determine the level of full or partial fulfillment of planned tasks, the reasons for their non-fulfillment, and existing obstacles. The status of achieving the set goals, as well as the reasons for failure to achieve them, are analyzed separately.

In addition, the positive aspects of the measures taken and the shortcomings committed will be studied, and further measures to eliminate them will be determined. These processes are discussed at the meeting of the mahalla seven under the leadership of the chairman, analyzed based on the submitted reports, and the results of cooperation activities are summarized through monitoring and reporting.

Mutual assistance and support in the joint performance of tasks. Interaction between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies is manifested in forms such as

"mutual assistance," "assistance," and "support." These forms are an important mechanism for practical cooperation in ensuring public safety and crime prevention.

At the same time, these relations are strictly regulated by regulatory legal acts. In particular, according to part two of Article 11 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies," state bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, and other organizations are obliged to assist internal affairs bodies in protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens, maintaining public order, ensuring public safety, preventing crimes and offenses, identifying and solving them, and locating missing persons.

Thus, cooperative relations have an imperative legal basis, and the fulfillment of the tasks defined in them is mandatory for all subjects. This requires avoiding procrastination and ensuring the effectiveness of cooperation.

Conclusions and recommendations. Cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies serves as a vital institutional mechanism for ensuring public safety and the early prevention of offenses. Analysis shows that although the legal framework for this cooperation has been sufficiently formed, in practice, consistency between planning, execution, and evaluation of results is not always ensured. Furthermore, the lack of systematic organization of preventive measures in certain cases negatively affects their effectiveness.

In this regard, it is necessary to improve cooperation processes based on the principle of single-cycle management—that is, to ensure an organic link between planning, implementation, and evaluation of results. Through the further integration of digital information systems, it is advisable to strengthen information exchange and control mechanisms, and to introduce specific performance indicators for preventive measures. At the same time, it is necessary to increase accountability and executive discipline in the activities of responsible entities at the mahalla level, and when analyzing results, to apply not only reporting but also scientific-practical assessment and forecasting approaches.

In general, the priority direction for the development of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and mahalla institutions is the introduction of a digitalized management system, increasing the efficiency of implementation, and strengthening practical mechanisms aimed at achieving results.

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